

IMPROVING PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN VIA TEACHING THEM TO SWIM FROM INFANCY

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ANNOTATION

The main form of organizing and conducting swimming lessons is a group lesson, which embodies the entire educational process. The task, content and direction of each lesson are determined based on the tasks and educational material set before the course, as well as the knowledge and skills of the participants acquired in the previous lessons.

Key words:

Swimming lessons, Children's health activities, Basics and methods of training, Planning and content of training lessons, Methods of organizing training for children and teenagers.

АННОТАЦИЯ

Основной формой организации и проведения занятий плаванием является групповое занятие, воплощающее в себе весь учебный процесс. Задача, содержание и направленность каждого урока определяются исходя из задач и учебного материала, поставленных перед курсом, а также знаний и навыков участников, приобретенных на предыдущих уроках.

Ключевые слова:

Уроки плавания, Оздоровительная деятельность детей, Основы и методы обучения, Планирование и содержание тренировочных занятий, Методика организации тренировок детей и подростков.

Teaching children to swim from infancy is very important to improve their physical development. In this case, tasks such as mastering the technique of swimming, development and improvement of movement qualities of participants are solved in the main part of the lesson. This can include elements of swimming techniques, teaching and mastering start and turn techniques, showing deficiencies in the quality of the exercises performed by the participants of the taught swimming style, and giving some warnings of educational importance.

It is necessary to take into account their unique anatomical, physiological and psychological characteristics when organizing and implementing the initial swimming training of children. There is no fundamental difference between the methodology of primary training of swimming for children and adults. However, when the teacher works with children, it is necessary to use methodological methods depending on their age characteristics and capabilities. When teaching children to swim, methods of explanation and demonstration are used widely. When working with young children, demonstration is combined with explanation in a light and easy form. A full and deeper explanation using visual aids is necessary in teaching middle and older children. It is necessary to take into account that children's minds are sharp when accepting what they see. Therefore, the presentation must be accurate and competent. The quality of swimming technique acquisition and the sports future of students largely depends on the quality of performance. It is absolutely impossible to allow children to perform the swimming technique incorrectly and sloppy during the exercises. It is necessary to correct every movement of children who have mastered swimming technique in a general, rough form. However, children aged 5-8 usually do not know how to swim at all, and many of them do not dare to enter the water independently and perform even the simplest exercises. Even when swimming on their own with an inflatable circle, their legs and arms still move like they do when they walk. In this case, the head is raised above the surface of the water. As a result, the legs sink deep into the water, the body becomes almost vertical, and it becomes almost impossible to move in the water. It is difficult for children aged 5-8 years to memorize the exercises shown in the water and they are slow to accept verbal explanations. They perform the indicated and explained exercises or some swimming movements with great difficulty. At the same time, they need the teacher's direct, spiritual support. Therefore, it is advisable for the teacher to be in the water until the children learn to confidently enter the water independently and perform swimming exercises. The direct involvement of the teacher encourages them and helps to teach swimming movements correctly. For example, children hold a special handle on the edge of the pool with their hands, and in order to perform leg movements correctly, the teacher should help them to stand horizontally by holding their leg around the knee or boulder-paw joint. When teaching swimming on the chest or lying on the back with the help of leg movements, the teacher walks next to or in front of the child, holds him by the elbow and helps him perform hand movements. Exercises are performed with the help of a swimming belt, then without a belt. Before starting to teach sports swimming techniques, it is necessary to use a complex of special preparatory exercises aimed at mastering the water environment.

There is a big difference between these exercises and the exercises performed during the primary education of older and middle-aged children.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to organize water training exercises for children aged 5-8 years as follows:

Immersion of the child in water, including first up to the chest, then up to the shoulder girdle and completely with the head. In this case, the exercise should be carried out while holding the child by the hand. At the same time, it is very important to teach a child to hold his breath while submerged.

The same as the previous exercise. It is done by holding the child's hand and only without immersing it in water. The teacher swims in the breaststroke method or is immersed in water up to the neck, holding the child's back or his shoulders.

A child lying on the breast is held by the hand, until the head is submerged in water, and while lying on the back, the child swims on the back by holding the armpit or the head.

The teacher helps the children to stand horizontally (on the chest and on the back) and to maintain this position by holding the child's lower back and abdomen. a) next to the body; b) forwarded; c) one hand is stretched forward, the other is next to the body; g) it is helped in cases where the elbows are written to the sides and the palms are placed behind the head (only when lying on the back).

These exercises are performed first standing in one place, and then moving together with the teacher.

When children slide from one teacher to another in the water, they are helped to maintain a horizontal position (in different positions of the hands, lying on the chest and on the back); The horizontal position is maintained when sliding from the teacher to the edge of the pool, from the edge of the pool to the teacher, using the speed calculated by the teacher's tool (lightly pushing) or from the edge of the pool with his foot.

Lying on the back, with the help of leg movements (in different positions of the hands), they swim in groups across the width and height of the pool. Teachers stand on the edge of the pool and observe and guide. They give necessary instructions to the children about keeping the body in the water correctly, swimming movements of the legs and breathing correctly. Children are taught to move their legs while lying on their backs (in different positions of their hands) and to match them with leg movements and breathing in the following sequence:

While lying on his back, he swims by leg movements, the teacher follows and corrects the movements of the hands by walking next to or in front of the child. The teacher holds the child's elbow and helps him perform hand movements.

He lies on his back and swims across the pool. The teacher walks next to the child and observes him, showing him hand movements and breathing and exhalation.

Lying on his back, he swims along the length of the pool. The teacher floats next to the child and becomes his eyes and ears.

That's why. The teacher walks along the edge of the pool (with and without a stick) and shows the child hand movements and matching them with breathing.

After the above-mentioned exercises are thoroughly mastered, it is possible to teach starting jumps. Turns are taught directly with the help of a teacher. The teacher demonstrates the turn in the water and teaches it together with diving and retrieving objects from the bottom of a shallow pool. The instructor first dives with each child, then watches them dive independently in turn. The process of teaching children to swim at the age of 9-10 is basically similar to the process of teaching middle-aged, older and adults to swim. But in the first stage of training, the teacher is in the water to conduct general preparatory exercises for mastering the water and to show the children the execution of the exercises for mastering the foot movement technique and to supervise them and provide assistance if necessary. is necessary.

An atmosphere of cheerfulness should be created in each of the classes dedicated to entertaining games, whether on land or in water. It excites the children, improves their mood and increases their enthusiasm for the next lessons. For this, the teacher must mobilize all his experience, skills and abilities.

It is known that human health is directly related to many areas. In this, medical and hygienic requirements, rest, food, sleep, and cultural recreation are of great importance. In their composition, realistic movement (swimming, running, jumping, lifting, breathing, etc.) is considered the most important. Physical exercises, sports, trips, trips and national games of the people can fully serve to improve the quality and improvement of natural movements. Together with the content of physical culture and sports focusing on certain goals, they are directed to the education of the physical fitness of the population, especially young people and students. This makes a spiritually and physically well-developed person. Therefore, physical education, sports, travel and national games of the people acquire their own characteristics in the context of a healthy lifestyle.

We know that in our country, in order to increase the productivity of work in educational institutions, enterprises and factories, industrial gymnastics, which is part of the fitness gymnastics tour, is being supported. Industrial gymnastics helps to strengthen the health of workers, and on this basis contributes to the increase of labor productivity. In the same way, in order to widely promote "Morning physical education" in all educational institutions of our country, including general secondary

schools, 10-15 minutes before the start of classes, students and teachers Together, morning physical training exercises are performed to the accompaniment of music, and the students' psychological and physiological moods are improved, and they ensure that they start the lessons in an upbeat mood. Of course, morning physical education is the basis for ensuring that a person is physically fresh and energetic during the day, and his mood is at an excellent level, and most importantly, the productivity of work and study during the day, as well as human energy.

It is known that physical education and its means (general development exercises, games, sports, hiking, trips, etc.) have their own characteristics, that is, active practical actions (physical education and sports) as a result, it moves all the joints and muscles in the human body. Regular physical training and sports ensure physical fitness. In this case, breathing speeds up and deepens, the blood circulation system warms the body and nourishes cells and tissues well. Also, physical exercises directly serve to digest food and calm and strengthen the nerves. On this basis, health improvement, physical training and training of sports skills are carried out. When performing these actions, it is necessary to take into account the age, gender, and health of the participants. Therefore, physical exercise is a source of health, stamina and fitness.

Exercises vary in form and content. They can be divided into the following main groups: morning hygienic gymnastics exercises, that is, body movements, especially various movements that use the joints (walking, running, jumping, bending, turning, swinging, stretching, etc.). Doing comprehensive physical activities during free time (on weekends, evenings and mornings). In this case, it is on the way to a specific goal (it is possible to exercise, gain strength). Almost all exercises and movements are performed in a unique way, and the standards of performance are also different. For example: someone does the exercise of sitting in the standing place quickly, and someone slowly. Someone can repeat this exercise 5-10 times, and someone can repeat it 20-30 times. These types of situations can be found in all types of training and active activities.

Therefore, it is necessary for teachers and everyone to know the ways, amounts, and sizes of exercises to choose and manage them depending on the health and physical condition of the participant. We must ensure that students in pre-school educational institutions or general education schools engage in activities that are appropriate for their age, both physically and mentally. That is, every teacher, pedagogue or coach should distribute the load correctly. In order to train the child from a young age, they can be involved in heavy sports from the age of 6-8. As a result, it has a negative effect on the body of a child who has not yet trained and it is not ready physically for special

exercises. According to the experts the exercise for developing child's body, it should be given to the sport of swimming. As a result, the child will be trained, both physically and mentally, and their body will be ready for special exercises.

Conclusion

To conclude, it can be noted that the methods of explanation and demonstration are used widely when we teach children to swim. Especially when working with young children, it is appropriate to show and explain in the light and easy form. It is necessary to provide a full and deeper explanation to use visual aids for teaching of older and middle-aged children. It should be taken into account that children's minds are sharp when accepting what they see. Therefore, it is very important that the presentation is correct and competent. Therefore, the quality of mastering swimming techniques and the sports future of students largely depends on the quality of performance. During the exercises, it is necessary to avoid incorrect execution of the technique of swimming movements, and it is necessary to correct each movement of children who have mastered the technique in a general, rough form. Children who aged 5-8 years old are usually do not know how to swim at all, so they need direct, spiritual support from the teacher. Therefore, it is better for the teacher to be in the water until the children can confidently enter the water independently and learn swimming exercises.

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